

Relational Knowledge in ANNs in the Context of Transfer Learning

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1. Abstract

Encoding and manipulating relational information is central to both human cognition and artificial intelligence. Humans excel at applying relational structures across domains such as numerical order, spatial relations, and linguistic syntax (Lake et al., 2016). Transferring abstract knowledge between contexts underpins flexible problem solving and creative reasoning. In artificial systems, despite the success of deep learning on image recognition and language processing, learning relational tasks and extracting abstract relational representations remain challenging (Santoro et al., 2017). In this work, we analyze the combination of comparison-based tasks with ordering tasks in artificial neural networks (ANNs), with the aim of understanding how learning an abstract concept can facilitate performance on different but related tasks.

2. Related Work and Theoretical Background

The study of abstract relational representations has deep roots in cognitive science. Early models proposed that abstract concepts arise as distributed neural patterns encoding relational properties (Kemp & Tenenbaum, 2008). In ANNs, research shows that that latent spaces can reflect

relational structures. For instance, Yang et al. (2019) found that recurrent neural networks (RNN) trained on diverse cognitive tasks form specialized yet overlapping activity clusters, suggesting that abstract relational representations can emerge despite surface-level task differences. In the context of Transitive Inference (TI), prior studies have shown that when networks are trained on adjacent pair comparisons, they can successfully generalize to non-adjacent items, thereby inferring a global linear order. This result is significant because it implies that the network is not simply memorizing pairwise relationships but is instead constructing a more general, abstract representation. (Di Antonio et al., 2024; Lippl et al., 2024)

Transfer learning, which accelerates learning on new tasks using pre-trained representations, is well-studied in domains like computer vision and language processing. However, most research focuses on tasks with shared low-level features. Here, we explore how an abstract relational representation learned from minimal symbolic inputs can transfer to a more complex sequential task. Using an RNN Sorting Task, we test whether initializing the network with a pre-trained representation from the TI task facilitates downstream learning. In addition, we explore how concurrent training on two related tasks facilitates performance, and examine representational similarity in this setting.

3. Methods

We examine two analogous task structures, both of which involve quantifying the effect of a Transitive Inference type task on a second task related to sorting.

3.1. Transitive Inference (TI) Task

In this work we use Transitive Inference (TI), a fundamental relational learning task, to induce a latent linear order in ANNs (Jensen, 2017). Items, represented as abstract vectors, have no predefined features or relations. The network is trained on adjacent pairs (e.g., $A > B$, $B > C$) and tested on non-adjacent pairs (e.g., $A > C$) to assess its ability to infer the correct order.

3.2. Ordinal Tasks

We compared another set of related tasks: they involved random sequences of integers as input and binary labels as targets. The sequence lengths were 2 and 5 for task one and two respectively. In both tasks random integers were sampled from range (0,100) for training and (100,200) for testing. Labels were assigned based on a similar notion of order: for task one label 1 corresponded to when item at index 0 was smaller and label 0 to the opposite cases. In task two label 1 was assigned when item at index 2 remained in the same position after sorting the sequence (ascending) and 0 otherwise. A feedforward network with three hidden layers was trained separately for each task. A third multi-task network, sharing three hidden layers but with separate input layers, was trained alternately on both tasks.

3.3. Integration into a Downstream RNN Sorting Task

To assess the transferability of abstract relational representations, we integrated the latent space from the TI task into an RNN tasked with sorting sequences. The RNN processes item pairs and reconstructs the sorted order based on a preset ranking shared with the TI task (**Fig 1.1C**, **Supplemental 8.2**). We compared five RNNs with different encoder layers:

1. **Model 1:** Frozen pretrained on TI; latent rank order is strongly linear (**Fig 1.1A**).
2. **Model 2:** Frozen pretrained on TI; latent rank order is of lower quality.
3. **Model 3:** Frozen, randomly initialized.
4. **Model 4:** Trainable, randomly initialized.
5. **Model 5:** Frozen, pretrained specifically on the Sorting Task.

During integration, activations from the pretrained network’s hidden layer, capturing abstract order, were used to initialize the RNN’s hidden state. The RNN was then fine-tuned using sequence-to-sequence learning with a loss function penalizing order deviations. Performance was assessed by convergence speed and final sorting accuracy.

4. Results

4.1 RNN Sorting Task Results

The five models displayed significant performance differences. Although four eventually reached zero loss and 100% training accuracy, convergence speeds varied (**Fig. 1.1B**):

- **Model 1 (Frozen TI with High-Quality Rank Order):** Converged the fastest. The clear representation of rank order provided by the TI pretraining enabled rapid learning in the sorting task (**Fig. 1.B.1**).
- **Model 5 (Frozen Pretrained on Sorting Task):** The model pretrained directly on the RNN sorting task was the second-best. Notably, the performance of Model 1 surpassed

that of Model 5, indicating that pretraining on the TI task can be more beneficial than pretraining on the Sorting Task itself (**Fig. 1.1B.5**).

- **Model 2 (Frozen TI with Lower-Quality Rank Order):** Ranked third. Although it had achieved 100% generalization accuracy on the TI task, knowledge of rank order was likely not concentrated in the encoder, resulting in slower convergence and lower initial performance when used as a frozen pretrained layer in the RNN (**Fig. 1.1B.2**).
- **Model 4 (Trainable Randomly Initialized):** This model performed better than the frozen randomly initialized model, converging to 100% accuracy albeit at a slower rate than Models 1, 5, and 2. The ability to adapt the hidden layer during training allowed the network to gradually acquire the necessary relational structure (**Fig. 1.1B.4**).
- **Model 3 (Frozen Randomly Initialized):** This model was the worst performer, failing to converge within 100 epochs. As the hidden layer was kept frozen and lacked any pretraining, it did not adapt to the sorting task, highlighting the importance of either pretraining or allowing trainable adjustments (**Fig. 1.1B.3**).

Importantly, these results show that using early layers pretrained on TI (**Fig 1.1B.1**) was just as effective — or better — than using early layers pretrained on the Sorting Task itself (**Fig 1.1B.5**), allowing for faster learning. This suggests that representations learned on TI may be more universally useful.

Figure 1

1.1 A. Model 1: Rank order in latent representations is strongly linear (Higher Quality)

1.1 B. Batch loss histories as a measure of learning curves

1.1 C. Model architectures: integration of TI Task and the RNN Sorting Task (**Supp 8.2**)

1.2 A. Ordinal tasks' results: RDM of multitask model

1.2 B-C Ordinal tasks' results: RDM of fine-tuned models

Fig 1.1 RNN Sorting Task Results

Fig 1.2. Ordinal tasks' results: RDM of multi-task & fine-tuned models

4.2 Ordinal Task Results

For the two ordinal tasks using integer sequences, the evaluation results on all three models showed high accuracy. Representational Dissimilarity Matrices (RDM - **Fig. 1.2A**) and Representational Similarity Analysis (RSA) on the last hidden layer activations averaged across epochs revealed higher similarity between single-task models and the multitask model but very small negative value between the single-task models.

The multi-task network was then pre-trained on only task one, fine-tuned with few epochs on task two, and tested on both, achieving moderate accuracy on task one (fine-tuning caused a decline in accuracy for task one) and task two. The process was repeated by reversing task order, giving high accuracies on both tasks.

RSA results on the single task models and the fine-tuned models showed high similarity between the network trained on task one and the network only fine-tuned on task one. The same was observed for task two (**Fig. 1.2C**). This suggest the representations from task two (involving the longer sequences) were more readily generalisable for task one and resulted in very little “catastrophic forgetting”. This was more of an issue for the reversed case. The observation is expected, since task two is more complicated than task one: identifying and tracking the fixed index in the sequence of length 5 instead of 2.

7. Conclusions

This study investigates the formation and transfer of abstract relational representations in ANNs. Our experiments confirm that tasks like Transitive Inference produce a latent linear rank order in

feedforward networks. More importantly, this abstract representation can be effectively transferred to a downstream RNN tasked with sorting sequences.

The integration of the pre-trained latent representation into the RNN resulted in consistent improvements in learning efficiency. Likewise, the concurrent training of a TI-like task using integers together with a sorting task improves performance on the latter, more challenging task. Our analyses indicate that the latent structure is able to facilitate complex sequential operations. These results underscore the potential of abstract relational representations as a foundation for transfer learning and have potential implications for the design of adaptive neural systems.

Our work sheds light on how abstract relational information is encoded and reused in ANNs. The improved success of the two ordinal tasks suggests that acquired representations serve as a stable, generalizable scaffold that can be applied across a wide range of cognitive tasks. As research in this area continues to evolve, we anticipate that further insights into the mechanisms underlying abstract relational reasoning will lead to the development of more efficient, flexible, and biologically inspired learning systems.

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